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NEW INSCRIPTIONS FROM THE TOKAT MUSEUM I

Abstract: This paper presents 10 new funerary inscriptions from the Tokat Museum. Some of the stelai are from Gaziura (no. 1), Zela (nos. 2 and 10) and Comana Pontica (no. 4). The places of discovery of the other stelai remain unknown. The oldest stele (no. 1) is from the late Classical or early Hellenistic Period. It was set up for a Rhodian who may have lived in Gaziura as a trader. The latest monument (no. 10) is a stele of a *chartularius* from the the end of the 5th or from the 6th century AD. The stele no. 3, which indicates the year 182 (Pontus Poleminiacus *era*), may have been set up in 245/46 AD. Of the names mentioned in the inscriptions, 11 are Greek and 7 Latin; the origin of “Sapos” in the stele no. 5 remains uncertain. The inscriptions suggest a high degree of Hellenization and Romanization in Pontus Polemoniachus.

In the late 1980ies a French team led by Bernard Rémy copied 25 inscriptions in the Tokat Museum. Of these, only 5 have been published to date.¹ In the summers of 2004 and 2005 we copied 36 inscriptions² in the said museum, ten of which are presented below. Inscription no. 1 is from Gaziura (Turhal), nos. 2 and 10 from Zela (Zile) and no. 4 from Comana Pontica (Gümenek). The find spots of the other inscriptions are not known. Yet, they are likely to come from settlements within the boundaries of the vilayet Tokat, namely from Comana Pontica,³ Sebastopolis (Sulusaray),⁴ Neocaesarea (Niksar),⁵ Zela⁶ and Gaziura.⁷

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¹ B. Rémy – B. Le Guen-Pollet – B. Özcan – M. Amandry, Rapport de travaux épigraphiques et numismatiques au musée de Tokat en juillet 1988, AST 7, 1989, 519–526; B. Rémy – B. Özcan, Trois inscriptions impériales grecques du musée de Tokat (Turquie), EA 19, 1992, 119–123.

² 13 of them have already been published: SEG XVIII, 1962, no. 561 (Neocaesarea); AE 1986, no. 657; SEG XL, 1990, nos. 1166–1171; SEG XLII, 1992, nos. 1133–1135 (Comana Pontica); AE 1990, no. 896 (Zela/Pazar); AE 1990, no. 895 (Sebastopolis).

³ Comana Pontica is located 11 km northeast of Tokat. From this settlement and its territory 21 inscriptions have been published so far: 4 dedications (IGR III, no. 106; SEG XL, 1990, no. 1166; SEG XLII, 1992, no. 1133, 1135); 3 honorary inscriptions (IGR III, no. 107; SEG XLI, 1991, no. 1107; SEG XLII, 1992, no. 1134); 3 milestones (D. H. French, Roman Roads and Milestones of Asia Minor. Fasc. II: An Interim Catalogue of Milestones, British Institute of Archaeology at Ankara [Monograph no. 9], Ankara 1988, nos. 56, 948, 959); 1 of them is a boundary stone (SEG XL, 1990, no. 1171) and 10 are funerary inscriptions (CIG III, 4184; F. Cumont, Nouvelles Inscriptions du Pont, REG 15, 1902, 312ff. nos. 2–6; SEG XL, 1990, nos. 1167–1170).

⁴ From Sebastopolis, located 62 km southwest of Tokat, 61 inscriptions are published: 4 votive offerings (SEG XXXIX, 1989, nos. 1348–1350; SEG XLI, 1991, no. 1115); 4 dedications (T. B. Mitford, Inscriptiones Ponticae – Sebastopolis, ZPE 87, 1991, 192ff. nos. 7–10); 11 honorary inscriptions (SEG XXXIX, 1989, nos. 1351–1353; SEG XLI, 1991, nos. 1109–1114; SEG XLIX, 1999, no. 1802; Mitford, op. cit., 200ff. no. 12), 39 funerary inscriptions (SEG XXXIX, 1989, nos. 1354–1364; SEG XLI, 1991, nos. 1116–1133, 1137–1139; Mit-

The Inscriptions

1. Epitaph of Herakleides of Rhodos, son of Demetrios

White marble stele (inv. no. 7143) with projecting triangular gable with acroterion in each corner, found in Varvara street in Turhal (ancient Gaziura). Frame of pediment undecorated. Egg-and-dart moulding immediately below pediment. Shaft area below moulding is smooth and plain, with two flowers in high relief. Large, empty field between flowers and inscription.

H. 1.25m, W. 0.42m, D. 0.23m, L. 0.025–0.04m.

Ἡρακλείδης[ς]
 2 Δημητρίου
 Ῥόδιος.

Herakleides of Rhodos, son of Demetrios.

Date: 4th or 3rd century BC.

In respect of the material, letter forms, size and decoration, the stele of Herakleides is very similar to that of Dolazelmis from the same museum, published by B. Le Guen-Pollet,⁸ who pointed out that the stele of Dolazelmis closely resembles a 4th century BC stele from Apollonia in Bulgaria. The stele of Herakleides may be dated to the same period. Why this Rhodian was buried in Gaziura is not known. Perhaps he was a settler (*metoikos*) there or a trader who died while travelling through the country. Interestingly, our Herakleides was a foreigner just like Dolazelmis, whom B. Le Guen-Pollet believes to be of Thracian provenance. Perhaps the stelai of this type were set up for *metoikoi* in Gaziura.

ford, op. cit., 206 no. 15, 211ff. no. 19, 215 no. 22, 222ff. no. 27, 223 no. 28, 240 no. 51, 242ff. no. 22); 2 fragments (SEG XLI, 1991, nos. 1135–1136) and one mosaic inscription (SEG XL, 1990, no. 1173).

⁵ From Kabeira/Diospolis/Sebaste/Neocaesarea located 60 km northeast of Tokat 13 inscriptions are published: 1 votive offering [Cumont, *Inscriptions du Pont* (n. 3), 314 no. 8]; 5 milestones [French, *Roman Roads* (n. 3), nos. 63, 937; G. Jerphanion – L. Jalabert, *Inscriptions d'Asie Mineure* (Pont, Cappadoce, Cilicie), *Mélanges de l'Université Saint Joseph, Beyrouth, Beirut* 3, 1908, 441 nos. 1–2; M. Christol – T. Drew-Bear – M. Özseit, *Trois Miliars d'Asie Mineure, Anatolia Antiqua* 2, 1993, 159ff. no. 1]; 4 funerary inscriptions (SEG XVIII, 1962, no. 561; Cumont, op. cit., 314 no. 7a, 334 no. 54; G. Jerphanion – L. Jalabert, op. cit., 444 no. 4); 3 fragments (W. J. Hamilton, *Researches in Asia Minor, Pontus and Armenia. With some Account of their Antiquities and Geology*. Hildesheim – Zürich – New York 1984², 346 nos. 1–2; Cumont, op. cit., 314 no. 7b).

⁶ Zela is located 70 km west of Tokat, from where 25 inscriptions are published to date: 2 votive offerings (J. G. C. Anderson – F. Cumont – H. Grégoire, *Studia Pontica III, Recueil des inscriptions grecques et latines du Pont et l'Arménie*, fasc. I, Brüssel 1910, no. 260–261, nos. 260–261); 2 honorary inscriptions (Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, op. cit., no. 271; Cumont, *Inscriptions du Pont* (n. 3), 318, no. 13); 3 milestones (French, *Roman Roads* (n. 3), no. 972; AE 1905, no. 132; D. R. Wilson, *Two Milestones from Pontus*, AS 10, 1960, 133ff. no. 1) and 18 funerary inscriptions (Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, op. cit., nos. 262–270, 272–277).

⁷ From Gaziura located 48 km west of Tokat 6 inscriptions had been published: Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, *Studia Pontica III* (n. 6), nos. 278, 278a 1–2, 278b–e.

⁸ Rémy – Le Guen-Pollet – Özcan – Amandry, *Rapport* (n. 1), 523.

2. Epitaph of Iulia Gemella and Lucius Pacilius Rufus

Tall, rectangular marble stele (inv. no. 7271) found in the town of Pazar in the territory of Zela. Triangular pediment with acroterion in each corner; rosette in centre of pediment; frame of pediment undecorated. Large empty field below inscription. Base somewhat wider than the shaft.

H. 1.91m, W. 0.41–0.37m, D. 0.125–0.225m, L. 0.03–0.045m.

Ἰουλία
Γέμελλα
γυνή δέ
4 Δέκμου
Πακελλίου.
Λούκιος Πα-
κελλίος
8 Ῥούφος
χαίρει.

*Iulia Gemella, wife of Decimus
Pacilius, (lies here). L. Pacilius Rufus
(erected the stele). Salute!*

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be from 3rd century AD.

L. 1–2: The nomen Gemellus is known from Zile.⁹

L. 6–7: Πακελλίος is probably the Greek version of the nomen Pacelius (or Pacilius/ Πακίλιος);¹⁰ it is known from Bithynian Claudiupolis where the name was found as written Πακήλιος.¹¹ According to F. Münzer, this gentilicium is of Oscian origin.¹²

The Roman names suggest an Italian provenance. One of the earlier members of the family may have been a veteran who had settled in Zela, perhaps at the time when Pompeius was making his arrangements, or during the military expeditions against Parthia in the 2nd and 3rd centuries AD. Z. Çizmeli did not touch on this matter in her recently published catalogue of coins from Neocaesarea.¹³ To ascertain whether there was a settlement of veterans in Zela, a thorough examination of the military history of the Pontus Polemoniacus area would be required, which, however, goes beyond the scope of this article.

⁹ Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, *Studia Pontica* III (n. 6), no. 264.

¹⁰ For the writing Πακίλιος, s. A. Maiuri, *Nuova Silloge Epigraphica di Rodi e Cos*, Firenze 1925, no. 631; IG XII.8, no. 532; cf. P. M. Fraser – E. Matthews, *A Lexicon of Greek Personal Names I*, Oxford 1987, 357.

¹¹ F. Becker-Bertau, *Die Inschriften von Klaudiu Polis*, Bonn 1986 (IK 31), no. 31; cf. H. Solin – O. Salomies, *Repertorium nominum gentilium et cognominum Latinorum*, Hildesheim – Zürich – New York 1994, 135.

¹² F. Münzer, *RE* XVIII,2 (1942), 2081 s. v. Pacilius; cf. Becker-Bertau, *IvKlaudiu Polis* (n. 11), 46.

¹³ Z. Çizmeli, *Le monnayage de Néocésarée et du koinon du Pont*, Milano 2006.

3. Epitaph of Theodora

Marble stele (inv. no. 7213) with incised pediment. Traces of three acroteria in each corner of the pediment. Centre of pediment with circular motif and three leave-like sections. Garland in high relief between pediment and inscription. Inscription on front face of shaft.

H. 0.65m, W. 0.295m, D. 0.22m, L. 0.03–0.025m.

Αὐρ. Πο-
 ὕλχερ τῆ
 εἰδίᾳ γυν-
 4 ἐκὶ Θεοδώ-
 ρῃ μνήμη-
 ς χάρειν
 ἔτους
 8 ρπβʹ.

*Aur(elius) Pulcher, (erected this stele) for his wife,
 Theodora, in memory. Year 182.*

Date: year 182 = AD 245/6(?) (Pontus Polemoniacus era).

Beside the era of Pontus Polemoniacus (valid in Neocaesarea, Zela, Trapezus, Kerasos, Sebasteia and for the Koinon of Pontos), the local era of Comana Pontica and Sebastopolis is known. The era of Pontus Polemoniacus starts in AD 64/5,¹⁴ while the local erae of Sebastopolis and Comana Pontica begin from 3/2 BC¹⁵ and from AD 34/5¹⁶ respectively. It seems likely that the given era is that of Pontus Polemoniacus which is also valid in Zela, since the shape and the ornaments of the stele recall those of the stelai from Zela.¹⁷ Eight persons are known from Pontus who bear the cognomen Pulcher/Pulchra. Four of these are from Zela,¹⁸ while the other four are from Neoclaudiopolis in Phazemonitis.¹⁹ This suggests a Zelean provenance. Consequently, the stele can be dated to AD 245/6.

L. 3–4: For γυνεκί = γυναικί.²⁰

L. 4–5: Θεοδώρη = Θεοδώρα.

L. 6: χάρειν = χάριν.²¹

¹⁴ W. Leschhorn, *Antike Ären. Zeitrechnung, Politik und Geschichte im Schwarzmeerraum und in Kleinasien nördlich des Tauros*, Stuttgart 1993 (Historia Einzelschriften 81), 135–143, 471–474.

¹⁵ Leschhorn, *Antike Ären* (n. 14), 119ff., 469f.; cf. Chr. Marek, *Stadt, Ära und Territorium in Pontus-Bithynia und Nord-Galatia*, Tübingen 1993, 57.

¹⁶ Leschhorn, *Antike Ären* (n. 14), 124ff., 470; cf. Marek, *Stadt, Ära und Territorium* (n. 15), 62 n. 417, 79.

¹⁷ Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, *Studia Pontica III* (n. 6), nos. 263, 265, 267, 272: s. esp. 265.

¹⁸ Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, *Studia Pontica III* (n. 6), nos. 265, 272 (masc.); no. 265 (fem.).

¹⁹ Anderson – Cumont – Grégoire, *Studia Pontica III* (n. 6), nos. 37, 40, 41 (fem.); no. 41 (masc.).

²⁰ For the use of ε for αι, s. F. T. Gignac, *A Grammar of the Greek Papyri of the Roman and Byzantine Periods I*, Milano 1976, 192.

²¹ For the use ει instead of ι, s. Gignac, *Grammar* (n. 20), 190.

4. Antonia I(ulia) Maxima to her mother Antonia Cleopatra

Tall, rectangular marble stele (inv. no. 7197). Found in the village of Akbelen in the territory of Comana Pontica. Top part missing (probably featured a pediment with acroteria). Well preserved inscription on the shaft. Large empty field above inscription. Abbreviation mark behind iota in second line.

H. 1.52m, W. 0.43m, D. 0.23m, L. 0.05m.

Ἄντωνί-
α Ἰ(ουλία) Μαξι-
μα Ἄντω-
4 νία Κλε-
οπάτρη
μητρί
μνήμη[ς]
8 χάριν.

*Antonia Iulia Maxima for her mother,
Antonia Cleopatra, in memory.*

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be from the 3th century AD.

L. 4–5: Κλεοπάτρη = Κλεοπάτρα.

5. Epitaph of Atia, daughter of Sapos

Rectangular marble stele (inv. no. 5986) with pediment flanked by acroteria decorated with half-palmettes. Top acroterion missing. Floral motif in centre of pediment. Frame of pediment undecorated. Inscription on front face of shaft defined by two plain plasters. Weather-worn circular motif divided into six sections below inscription.

H. 1.05m, W. 0.405m, D. 0.22m, L. 0.03–0.04m.

Ἄτια Σα-
2 που τοῖς
παράγου-
4 σι χάριν.

Atia, daughter of Sapo/as, salutes the passers-by.

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele is probably from the 3rd or the 4th century AD.

L. 1–2: The name Σαπος (or less likely Σαπας) has previously not been attested.²²

L. 4: χάριν for χάρειν.

²² Cf. Sapa, probably genitive of Sapas from Amphipolis: G. Mihailov, *Epigraphica Thracia*, *Epigraphica* 37, 1975, 30; s. also P. M. Fraser – E. Matthews, *A Lexicon of Greek Personal Names IV*, Oxford – New York, 2005, 304 s. v. Σαπας.

6. Epitaph of Philon and Hermeis

Rectangular basalt stele (inv. no. 5826) with half-palmette acroteria on either side and a circular one at the top, with six-leaved rosette in the centre. Front face of the shaft is divided into two panels. Rectangular panel with the head of a woman (Medusa?) above the inscription.

H. 0.82m, W. 0.37m, D. 0.075m, L. 0.04–0.025m.

Φιλοῦσα
Φίλωνι
καὶ Ἑρμεῖ
4 μνήμης
χάριν ἀ-
νέθηκεν.

*Philusa erected (this stele) for Philon
and Hermeis, in memory.*

Date: On the basis of the letter forms and the style, the stele appears to be from the 3rd or 4th century AD.

7. Epitaph of Chresime and her son

Top part of rectangular limestone stele which originally was probably composed of two pieces. Inscription above recessed arch. Letters unevenly spaced and irregular. Narrow spacing between letters in third line. Fourth line divided into two sections by said arch.

H. 0.34m, W. 0.29m, D. 0.11m, L. 0.015–0.03m.

Εὐχάριστος
2 Χρησίμη εἰδίᾳ
σὺβίῳ καὶ τέκνῳ μν[ή]-
4 μης χάριν.

*Eucharistos for his wife Chresime
and his son, in memory.*

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be either from the 3rd or 4th century AD.

L. 2: εἰδίᾳ for ἰδίᾳ.

L. 3: σὺβίῳ for συμβίῳ.

8. Epitaph of Dionysios, son of Dionysios

Rectangular marble stele. Stone damaged at top and bottom and on left-hand side. Inscription complete. Large ivy leaf incised before last letter in sixth line.

H. 0.33m, W. 0.13m, D. 0.03m, L. 0.02–0.025m.

Διονύ-
σ(ι)ος Διο-
νυσ{Υ}<ι>-
4 ου
ἐτῶν
κ'.

Dionysios, son of Dionysios (died) at the age of 20.

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be either from the 3th or 4th century AD.

L. 2: Gap for one or two letters after sigma.

9. Fragment of an epitaph

Rectangular basalt stele. Top of stele with first few lines of inscription missing; last line intact.

H. 0.75m, W. 0.535m, D. 0.14m, L. 0.045–0.05m.

[.....]
02 [. μν]-
[ήμης χ]άριν.
2 [χαίρ]ετε οἱ πα-
ράγοντες.

NN for NN in memory. Salute, o passers-by!

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be either from the 4th century AD or later.

10. Epitaph of Komitas, the keeper of the archive

Two joining fragments of white marble stele (inv. no. 7270) with round top from Zile. Recessed arch with a tabula ansata and a large cross with curved ends. Inscription in tabula ansata with two small crosses at the beginning and the end of text.

H. 1.45m, W. 0.64m, D. 0.18m, L. 0.03m.

+ Κομιτᾶ-
 ς χαρτουλάριο-
 ς εὐσεβῆ ζήσας βί-
 4 ον ἐνθάδε κατὰ-
 κίτε +.

Komitas the archive keeper, who lived piously, lies here.

Date: On the basis of the letter forms, the stele appears to be either from the late 5th or 6th century AD.²³

L. 1–2: For the name Κομιτᾶς, s. W. Pape – G. E. Benseler, *Wörterbuch der griechischen Eigennamen*, Braunschweig 1911, 691 s.v. Κομιτᾶς.

L. 2–3: *Chartoularioi* were employed in the offices of the praetorian prefects, *magistri militum*, etc. after AD 326.²⁴

²³ For an inscription of a chartularius from the same period (Caesarea in Palaestina), s. AE 1995, 1588.

²⁴ For the office, s. O. Seeck, *RE* III,2 (1899), 2193 s. v. chartularii; A. H. M. Jones, *The Later Roman Empire* (284–602), Oxford 1964, 587–589; cf. John Lydus, *de mag.* III, 17.20.

ÖZET

Tokat Müzesi'nden Yeni Yazıtlar I

Bu makalede Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı, Anıtlar ve Müzeler Genel Müdürlüğü'nün izniyle 2004–2005 yıllarında Tokat Müzesi'nde kaydedilen on mezar yazıtı tanıtılmaktadır. Buluntu yerleri belli olan steller müzeye Gaziura (no. 1), Zela (nos. 2 and 10) ve Comana Pontica'dan (no. 4) getirilmişlerdir. Diğer yazıtların buluntu yerleri bilinmemektedir. Makalede tanıtılan yazıtlardan en erkeni (no. 1) Erken Helenistik Dönem'e tarihlenen ve yaşamını Gaziura'da büyük olasılıkla tüccar olarak tamamlayan Rhodos'lu Herakleides'in mezar steli üzerindedir. Makalede tanıtılan en geç yazıt ise, *chartularius* olarak hizmet vermiş Komitas'a ait olup İS. V. ya da VI. yüzyıla tarihlenmektedir. Aurelius Pulcher'in eşi Theodora için diktiği mezar stelinde verilen 182 yılı büyük olasılıkla Pontus Polemoniacus *era*'sına göre hesaplanmış olmalıdır. Yazıtlarda anılan isimlerden on biri Yunan, yedisi ise, Latin kökenlidir. Beşinci sırada tanıtılan stelin andığı Sapos (ya da daha zayıf bir olasılıkla Sapas) isminin kökeni belirlenememektedir. Sonuç olarak burada ele alınan yazıtların ortaya çıkardığı tablo Hellen ardından da Roma kültürünün benimsenme sürecinin Pontus Polemoniacus'ta kaydettiği aşamayı yansıtmaktadır.

Yazıtların çevirileri şöyledir:

No. 1: *Demetrios oğlu, Rhodos'lu Herakleides (burada yatıyor).*

No. 2: *Decimus Pacilius'un eşi Iulia Gemella (burada yatıyor). (Bu steli) Lucius Pacilius Rufus (dikti). (Ey yolcu, rahmetliyi) selamla!*

No. 3: *Aurelius Pulcher, kendi karısı Theodora için, anısı vesilesiyle (dikti); yıl 182.*

No. 4: *Antonia Maxima, annesi Antonia Cleopatra için, anısı vesilesiyle (dikti).*

No. 5: *Sapos'un kızı Atia gelip geçenlere selam etmek üzere (bu steli yaptırdı).*

No. 6: *Philusa, Philon ve Hermeis için, anıları vesileleriyle (dikti).*

No. 7: *Eukharistos, kendi karısı Khresime ve oğlu için, anıları vesilesiyle (dikti).*

No. 8: *20 yaşında (ölen) Dionysios oğlu Dionysios (burada yatıyor).*

No. 9: *Falanca, falanca için, anısı vesilesiyle (dikti), Ey geçenler, selam olsun.*

No. 10: *Hayatı boyunca dindar bir yaşam süren, chartularios Komitas burada yatıyor.*